

PSYCHOLOGICAL CRISIS ON CHILD EXPERIENCE SEXUAL ABUSE: BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Psychological Crisis on Child Experience Sexual Abuse: Bibliometric Analysis

Siti Fitriana,* Ellya Rakhmawati, Suyitno
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Children who experience sexual abuse (CSA) are impacted by psychological crisis. The psychological vulnerability of these children can pose a serious threat to their mental health. This issue warrants critical attention, as sexual represents a profound societal challenge, and psychological crisis frequently emerge as a consequence of CSA. Therefore, an in-depth study of psychological crisis in children who experience sexual abuse is necessary. This study aims to analyze research on psychological crisis in children affected by sexual abuse using bibliometric analysis. The results indicate that data searchers using the keyword “psychological crisis,” “child sexual abuse,” and “victim” yielded 9.690 selected English-language articles. The total number of publications cited is 28,338, with 26,682 citations without self-citations. The average number of citations per article is 13.77. Further collaboration integrating both quantitative and qualitative indicators is necessary. The researchers hope that this study provides both theoretical and practical benefits, with a specific focus on addressing the psychological crises experienced by children who have been sexually abused. This study is expected to contribute for both academics and practitioners, providing a foundational bases for interdisciplinary collaboration and enhancing efforts in the prevention and intervention of psychological crises experienced by sexually abused children.

Keywords: *psychological crises, child sexual abuse, bibliometric*

Introduction

The incidence of sexual abuse in Indonesia, predominantly involving young children, has been steadily increasing. Victims of sexual abuse need psychological support and assistance to recover from traumatic events. Data from the Ministry of Women’s Empowerment and Child Protection (KemenPPA) reported a total of 24,158 cases of violence against children in 2023, with sexual abuse being the most prevalent, accounting for 10,932 cases. Children are particularly vulnerable to sexual abuse, even within their immediate surroundings, as they are often perceived as powerless, highly dependent to adults, and lacking in sexual awareness (Suhasma & Ismet, 2021); (Septiani, 2021); (Juniawati, 2015); (Juniawati, 2015).

Previous researchers mentioned that the majority of sexual abuse victims, particularly women who experienced victimization during childhood, often struggle with anger issue due to impaired emotional regulation and low self-esteem (Gardner et al., 2019); (Scott et al., 2018); (Weindl et al., 2020). Additionally, victims of sexual abuse may experience sleep disturbances, anger, suicidal tendencies, and long-term psychological effects, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), which can significantly impact their developmental trajectory (Briere & Elliott, 2003).

Generally, CSA impacts psychological well-being, often leading to psychological crises with symptoms including major depression, antisocial personality traits, substance abuse, and more (Molero-Zafra et al., 2022); (Gewirtz-Meydan & Finkelhor, 2020). CSA effects psychological, physical, and social functioning, potentially leading to psychopathological changes such as difficulty in self-acceptance, depression, sexual dysfunction, and various other sequelae (Pereda, et al., 2009); (Pereda, et al., 2009); (Hornor, 2010); (Brewin et al., 2000). Specialized interventions are needed to help these survivors to manage their traumatic experiences effectively (Molero-Zafra et al., 2022). Sexual education serves as an intervention strategy to reduce CSA cases, enabling children with information and knowledge to prevent sexual abuse (Andini et al., 2019).

Children who experience sexual abuse may display negative attitudes and behaviors, as well as destructive tendencies directed toward the perpetrators, whether they are parents, teachers, or individuals in their environment. These attitudes may manifest as difficulties in self-adjustment, socialization, depression, feelings of isolation, rejection, loss of desire in socializing with peers, and discomfort within peer groups (Amriana, 2015); (Brendgen et al., 2006). Victims may also face issues such as eating disorders, weight loss, sleep disturbances, fatigue, anxiety, frequent crying, slowed cognitive processes, suicidal thoughts, feelings of guilt, worthlessness, and hopelessness (Aldridge & Goldman, 2007). Other potential challenges that may appear include trouble concentrating, physical weakness, low motivation, antisocial behavior, and poor academic performance (Schwartz & Hopmeyer, 2003).

Given that sexual abuse against children is a serious issue with significant psychological aftereffect, this study is necessary to analyze research gaps through bibliometric analysis. Fundamentally, a psychological crisis is a condition in which an individual faces situation they perceive as obstacles to achieving their life goals.

Research Questions

The researchers aim to explore research trends on psychological crises in children affected by sexual abuse to understand its impact on their psychological well-being. The findings are expected to inform and guide future research direction, particularly in the area of child sexual abuse. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the bibliometric mapping of scientific publications on psychological crisis research and child sexual abuse in 2014-2024?
2. How is the visualization of the direction of development of research topics on psychological crises and child sexual abuse in 2014-2024?
3. How is the visualization of the collaborative authorship network or co-authorship network in scientific publications on research on psychological crises and child sexual abuse in 2014-2024?

Literature Review

Child Sexual Abuse (CSA)

CSA forms include being threatened and harassed, skirts being lifted, being kissed, abusive words, and so on (Andini TM, 2019). The problem of CSA is becoming very serious because the number is increasing every year (Coundry V, 2018; Kantor L, 2017). Boys and girls have experienced sexual violence through unwanted touching (Osadan, 2015). In fact, sexual violence can cause health and mental problems for victims, such as attempted suicide, post-traumatic stress disorder, and so on (Osadan, 2015). CSA is an act involving adults with minors through non-contact, and sexual contact (Guo S, 2019). KSA as a crime case that is often not reported by children (Waid-Lindberg, 2019) because the family feels ashamed (Ningrum, 2021). Researchers conclude that KSA is a crime case that is often not reported due to the shame experienced by the family so that the child experiences emotional disorders that have an impact on psychological crises.

Psychological Crisis

Crisis in Chinese means a state of hopelessness and an opportunity so that a crisis does not always have a bad impact, but instead indicates a very important point in a person's life (Peter, 2013). Therefore, a crisis can bring opportunities and also dangers if a method is not found to overcome it. Crisis itself is defined as a perception or experience of an event that is very heavy and difficult, and exceeds the capacity of individual resources and coping mechanisms (Silva, 2015). Individuals who experience a crisis will experience a crisis reaction that occurs immediately after the frightening event (Yeager, 2012).

This reaction can be in the form of feelings of shock, sadness, anger, despair, anxiety, and restlessness. Crisis conditions will always be faced by every individual. Individuals who cannot face crisis conditions will experience mental health disorders such as stress to depression. The state of psychological vulnerability for individuals can threaten mental health to become worse (Pertiwi, 2020). On the other hand, when individuals cannot adjust to the changes that occur, they will experience emotional crises such as feelings of anxiety, fear, ignorance, confusion, and feelings of helplessness (Rahmaf, 2023). At the stage of early childhood psychological development, psychological crises can begin to be experienced if children experience psychological disorders, especially due to sexual violence.

Methodology

This study employs bibliometric analysis using a quantitative approach, including author analysis, citation analysis, or keyword analysis, on bibliometric data (Baker et al., 2019; Ragazou et al., 2022). Bibliometric analysis aims to analyze publication trends, measure journal publication impact, and explore the development of specific topics in academic literature (Tran et al., 2018; Chen & Xie, 2020). The researchers intend to analyze publication topic related to child sexual abuse. This analysis is expected to provide insights of publication trends, developments, and collaboration among authors in their respective subject areas (Donthu, Kumar, Pattnaik, et al., 2021; Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, et al., 2021). Data search on psychological crisis and child sexual abuse were collected from the Web of Science database, encompassing the total population from 2000 to 2024 through www.webofscience.com as a reference for psychological crisis and child sexual abuse documents (Tran et al., 2018).

The analysis data techniques include collect basic characteristic of articles with keywords psychological crises, victims, and child sexual abuse (the number of authors in research articles, publication years, main categories in journal articles); search the most common to specific keywords related to CSA; the most productive authors (approximately 60 documents); countries with significant publication counts (more than 75 documents); highly impactful papers (cited more than 600 times). Keywords are identified using Wordle. Keyword trend analysis was utilized to examine changes in keyword prevalence over time, as well as to highlight emerging and developing topics. This approach aligns with the methodology outline by Passas, which serves as a reference for the authors in designing data analysis techniques using bibliometric analysis. The analysis aims to explore characteristics of scientific research on relevant subjects, including authors, institutions, countries, and citations patterns.

Previous studies have outlined specific steps to conduct bibliometric analysis, including data retrieval, bibliographic filtering, re-checking bibliographic attributes, and performing bibliometric analysis. These processes are supported by various software tools and websites for visualization such as Biblioshiny, Vosviewer, and Tableau. The data retrieval process involved collecting scientific articles using the keywords psychological crises, victims, and child sexual abuse (Passas, 2024); (İyibildiren et al., 2023); (Shu & Liu, 2021).

The data retrieval process was collected through the Web of Science platform and processed using VOSviewer and Biblioshiny to visualize network visualization and document analysis. In this study the researchers followed the following workflow: a) data collection, b) data screening and cleaning, c) data analysis, d) results and findings, and e) discussion and conclusion. Bibliometric

analysis was applied in detail across five stages: data collection, keyword selection, matrix relationship creation, result visualization, and data interpretation (Linnenluecke et al., 2020); (Aulianto et al., 2019).

Results and Discussion

The researchers collected data on November 18, 2024. Bibliometric methodology encapsulates quantitative techniques such as citation analysis or publication unit analysis (Klarin et al., 2023). Then, the researchers conducted six steps in performing Bibliometric analysis. In the first step, the researchers used keywords “psychological crises”, “child sexual abuse”, and “victim” to retrieve 54.317 documents. The second stage is reducing data by selecting documents categorized as articles, resulting 43.318 documents. Then, the researchers filtered for open-access documents, obtaining 13.023 documents. The next step is narrowing article scope to the last 10 years (2014-2024), yielding 10.909 documents. The last stage is selecting EN-language articles, resulting in 9.690 documents. Then, reducing document based on research area, that is psychology, to narrow the scope of documents area. Further data stage explanation is provided in table below.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Data

Stages	Inclusion Criteria	The total number of Document
1.	Document of data search on “psychological crisis”, “child sexual abuse”, and “victim” in database	54.317
2.	Document identified as article	43.318
3.	Document with open-access	13.023
4.	Document published in range of years 2014-2024.	10.909
5.	Document written in English-language	9.690
6.	Document in the scope of psychology area	2.058

Based on the research findings, the researchers present detail of discussion into sub-sections, including publication trends, the most common journal sources that publish CSA articles, lead authors information, author’s affiliation, and corresponding author’s countries.

Publication Trends

In the 10-year period from 2014 to 2024, a total of 2,058 documents were identified after filtering them six times using the keywords “child sexual abuse,” “psychological crisis,” and “victim.”

Figure 1 presents a statistical summary of article publications, illustrating the level of research productivity and its impact during this period. The scope of documents in the psychology area produced 2,058 articles from 354 publication sources. The annual growth rate of publications is 15.28%, indicating a significant increase in publication volume. Then, there were 21,949 total of citing articles, of which 21,134 were article without-self-citations. Self-citation refers to the practice of authors citing their own published article as a reference in new publications (Arifin et al., 2021). The total number of cited publications reached 28,338, with 26,682 citations coming from other authors excluding self-citations. The average number of citations per article is 13.77. An H-index of 66 signifies a significant impact, indicating that every 66 articles in dataset have each been cited at least 66 times.

Figure 1. Research data finding in the scope area of Psychology for the period 2014-2024

Figure 2 shows the publication spikes occurred twice, that are in period 2018-2019, with an increase of total 45 publications, and in period 2020-2021, which marked the largest increase with total 51 publications. Furthermore, in total citations the curve followed an upward trend, with its peak in 2023. Significant citation surges occurred twice: from 2018 to 2019 with 946 citations and from 2020 to 2021 with an increase of 1,283 total citations. However, the total citation curve shows a decline after 2023, despite the number of publications is relatively high. This indicates a decrease in the appeal or visibility of newer articles.

Figure 2. Publication graphic and Citation Curve of research data in the period 2014-2024

Journal Sources Most Frequently publish CSA articles

There are a total of 200 journal sources that have contributed in publishing 2,058 articles. The journal sources that most frequently publish research on child sexual abuse are FRONTIERS IN PSYCHOLOGY with 217 publications, JOURNAL OF INTERPERSONAL VIOLENCE with 212 publications, and CHILD ABUSE & NEGLECT with 138 publications. Five journals stand out as the most prolific are 1) Frontiers in Psychology, a Scopus-indexed Q2 journal with an H-index of 184, 2) Journal of Interpersonal Violence, a Q1-indexed journal with an H-index of 127, 3) Child Abuse & Neglect also a Q1-indexed journal with an H-index of 174, 4) Journal of Child Sexual Abuse, a Q2-indexed journal with an H-index of 52, publishing 71 articles, and 5) Journal of Family Violence, a Q1-indexed journal with an H-index of 93, which published 53 articles with significant increase in publications starting in 2022.

Figure 3. The Most Frequent Journal Publisher to Publish Scopus Articles

Meanwhile, there were 86 journal publishers selected by authors to publish articles with keywords “child sexual abuse,” “psychological crisis,” and “victim.” From the dataset of 2,058 articles, the most frequently used publisher is Sage, with 388 articles published, followed by Taylor & Francis with 334 articles, Elsevier with 299 articles, Wiley with 274 articles, and Frontiers Media SA with 217 articles. Other publishers selected by authors for publishing articles in psychology include Springer Nature with 179 articles, Educational Publishing Foundation with 49 articles, American Psychological Association with 44 articles, and MDPI with 27 published articles.

Authors

Based on the 2.058 articles, there are 6,361 total authors who have published articles with topic on psychological crises in children experience sexual abuse. Author productivity will be described by implementing Lotka's Law. Lotka's Law is a bibliometric laws that describes the relationship between the number of authors and their productivity in producing documents. The theoretical distribution of Lotka's Law is calculated using the formula:

- C Y(x) = the proportion of authors producing x document
- Y(x)= C = Constant
- Xn X = the number of articles written by an individual author
- N = the exponent, which is generally close to 2

Author	h_index	g_index	m_index	TC	NP	PY_start
LYON TD	13	18	1.182	419	18	2014
CHOPIN J	11	15	1.833	259	21	2019
BEAUREGARD E	10	15	1.667	238	20	2019
STOLZENBERG SN	10	15	0.909	269	15	2014
VEENSTRA R	9	10	0.900	207	10	2015
LANDSTRÖM S	8	11	0.727	142	11	2014
ULLMAN SE	8	11	0.727	410	11	2014
CILLESSEN AHN	7	9	0.636	157	9	2014
GOLLWITZER M	7	11	0.700	134	16	2015
HÉBERT M	7	11	0.700	250	11	2015

Figure 4. The Most Frequent Journal Publisher for publication

The curve in Figure 5 shows a negative exponential distribution, where the majority of authors that only write one document are around 84.4% (see the vertical axis), while the number of authors decreases drastically as the number of documents written increases (see the horizontal axis). According to the Lotka's Law table, there are 5,371 authors with one (1) document with total of percentage is 84.4%. Next, there are 629 authors with two (2) documents (9.9%), and 189 authors with three (3) documents (3.0%). After three documents, the number of authors continues to decrease drastically and levels off after writing more than five articles. There are 77 authors who wrote four (4) documents, representing 1.2%. Then, there are 45 authors with five (5) documents (0.7%) and 16 authors with six (6) documents (0.3%). The table shows that only one author wrote more than 15 documents. The data above supports Lotka's Law, where only a small number of authors are categorized as highly productive.

Figure 5. Lotka's Law Curve and Table

Based on annual productivity (m-index), Chopin J has the highest m-index (1.833), followed by Beauregard E (1.667), indicating very high annual productivity starting in 2019. Meanwhile, Lyon TD (1.182) and Stolzenberg SN (0.909) have lower indexes, reflecting stable contributions over a long period from 2014 to 2024. In terms of total citations, Lyon TD stands out with 419 citations from 18 publications, Ullman SE has 410 citations from 11 publications, and Stolzenberg SN received 269 citations from 15 publications, demonstrating the broad impact of the authors' publications within the academic community.

Figure 6. Authors' productivity table

Author's affiliation

Based on the biblioshiny graphic, the University of California System has a significant publication trend with the highest number of publications from 2014 to 2024, totaling 623 documents, followed by the University of London with 552 documents. Next, the Pennsylvania Commonwealth System of Higher Education (PCSHE) has 271 documents, Griffith University has 240 documents, and Pennsylvania State University has 199 documents. The publication production trends of the University of California System and Griffith University have shown the most consistent growth since 2014. Meanwhile, the University of London saw a significant increase after 2020. The Pennsylvania Commonwealth System of Higher Education (PCSHE) experienced a gradual increase in publications

from 2014 to 2018, with significant growth occurring in 2024. The publication growth of PCSHE is also seen at Pennsylvania State University.

Figure 7. Author's affiliation productivity (Biblioshiny) and Affiliation network (VOSviewer)

Corresponding Author's Countries

The affiliation network from VOSviewer illustrates the visualization of international collaboration networks based on co-authorship in scientific publications. It shows that the United States and the United Kingdom (UK) have the largest nodes, indicating that they are dominating the publications and collaborations of studies. Countries such as the UK, Australia, and China also play a significant role, as seen from the size of their nodes and the numerous connecting lines with other countries.

Figure 8. Corresponding author's countries from VOSviewer and Biblioshiny

Data from Figure 8 shows that the countries with the highest number of corresponding authors are the United States, followed by the United Kingdom, Australia, Spain, and the Netherlands. These countries play a dominant role in global research collaboration. The countries with the most article contributions are the United States with 442 articles (21.5%), the United Kingdom with 340 articles (16.5%), and Australia with 159 articles (7.7%). In the Biblioshiny graphic, the United States leads in publication with SCP (378 documents), accounting for around 85.5%, indicating that the articles were produced by authors from a single country. However, the MCP received 64 documents (14.5%), meaning the articles are the result of collaboration between authors from multiple countries. Countries with a high proportion of MCP include Israel (55.9%), the Netherlands (43.8%), and Italy (42.9%), reflecting that these countries primarily focus on cross-border collaboration. It can be concluded that developed countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia dominate publications related to psychological crises in children experience sexual abuse.

Conclusions

Conducting research with Bibliometric analysis aims to provide a strong foundational bases for further studies and in-depth exploratory research. The researchers have contributed to offer a comprehensive overview of the research findings. Bibliometric analysis was selected to provide knowledge related to development of a current research trends on psychological crises and child sexual abuse, as well as its challenging and directions for future studies, which can serve as a reference for the next research. This study uses only Scopus-based articles as research documents, considered more inclusive compared to other articles. However, this research limits documents with only use English-language articles, meaning that the researchers excluded relevant articles in other languages. This limitation affects the data completeness that may overlook valuable contributions in other languages research. Additionally, the researchers employed quantitative indicators and did not include qualitative indicators.

Based on the data result, data search findings with keywords psychological crisis, child sexual abuse, and victim, yielded 9.690 documents in English-language. The total number of publications cited is 28.338 documents and 26.682 documents without self-citation. The average number of citations per article is 13,77. The H-index of the document is 66, indicates that article publications have significant influence for the study, which means that every 66 articles in dataset have been cited at least 66 times.

The most common journal sources that publish child sexual abuse (CSA) as a research topic are FRONTIERS IN PSYCHOLOGY with 217 articles published, JOURNAL OF INTERPERSONAL VIOLENCE with 212 articles published, and CHILD ABUSE NEGLECT with 138 articles published. There are five journal publishers that publish the most psychology articles discussing CSA. Meanwhile, there are total 86 of journal publishers selected by authors to publish their articles with the keywords “child sexual abuse”, “psychological crises”, and “victim” in the scope area of psychology.

Further collaboration with both quantitative and qualitative indicators are necessary. This study is expected to provide theoretical and practical benefits focus on psychological crisis and child sexual abuse issues. The researchers hope that this study can be beneficial for academic and practitioners as a reference before conducting research collaboration from various perspectives and enhance prevention and intervention related to psychological crisis and CSA.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Siti Fitriana

University of PGRI – Indonesia

Ellya Rakhmawati

University of PGRI – Indonesia

Suyitno

University of PGRI – Indonesia